

Socio-Economic Impact of Covid-19 on People with Spinal Cord Injury in Bangladesh: A Telephonic Survey

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Abstract

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted global health systems and economies with people with disabilities, particularly those with spinal cord injuries (SCI). In Bangladesh, where healthcare resources are limited, persons with SCI face challenges in accessing necessary services and maintaining socio-economic stability during the pandemic. **Methods:** A quantitative cross-sectional study was conducted using a telephonic survey of 470 individuals with SCI who had completed rehabilitation at the Centre for the Rehabilitation of the Paralysed (CRP). Data were collected from both urban and rural areas across eight divisions of Bangladesh. The survey, consisting of semi-structured questionnaires, gathered information on demographic profiles, Covid-19 protection measures, and socio-economic impacts. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20. **Results:** The study shows the significant socio-economic disruptions among persons with SCI due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The majority of participants (87%) were male, with age distribution primarily between 21-40 years. Only 30% of participants took Covid-19 protection measures, and 18% received local emergency aid. Economic activities were adversely affected, with 52% reporting their business status as "bad" and 12% as "not good enough." Additionally, 78% required Covid-19 related support, highlighting the severe financial distress and need for assistance in this group of populations. **Conclusions:** The findings highlight the socio-economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on persons with SCI in Bangladesh. The findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to address the unique challenges faced by this vulnerable group. Policymakers and healthcare providers must prioritize inclusive and equitable responses to public health emergencies to ensure that no one is left behind.

More Information

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Introduction

The novel coronavirus (Covid-19) started to spread in Wuhan, China, in November 2019, after that on March 11th, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared Covid-19 a global pandemic [1]. Over 120 million cases and over 2.6 million verified fatalities were reported globally as of March 16, 2020 [2]. This pandemic situation is a public health crisis that has dramatically changed everyday life. Covid-19 has presented the challenges to participation in community, quality of life, and other health related issues, because it restricted the community participation and limits the access to daily necessities and services [3]. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly affected global health systems, economies, and societies at large. Among the most vulnerable populations are individuals with disabilities, particularly those with spinal cord injuries (SCI). People with SCI may be at a greater risk for adverse effects from the Covid-19 virus and have additional difficulties obtaining daily necessities because of limitations in ability to complete tasks in the community.

SCI can be simply put as damage to the spinal cord and can be caused by several factors, such as, disease, degeneration, or trauma [4]. SCI is a devastating event and the global incidence rate of over 200,000 cases per year [5]. It has a massive impact on the person with SCI, the family members, and also in community with an estimated lifetime cost of care of £1.12 million in the United Kingdom [6]. These individuals face unique challenges, including heightened health risks and socio-economic vulnerabilities, which have been exacerbated by the pandemic. Understanding the specific impacts on this group is crucial for developing targeted interventions and support mechanisms. SCI is a life-altering condition that significantly impairs physical function and mobility, often requiring long-term medical care and rehabilitation [7]. In developing countries, the burden of SCI is compounded by limited healthcare resources and inadequate social support systems [8]. The Covid-19 pandemic has further strained these systems, making it even more difficult for individuals with SCI to access necessary services and support.

Family members support enabling an individual to feel protected and free to fulfill their potential. Family roles are affected and restructured due to SCI [9]. Bangladesh, a densely populated country with a developing healthcare infrastructure, has faced significant challenges in managing the spread of COVID-19. Lockdowns, social distancing, and the reallocation of healthcare resources to combat the pandemic have

disrupted routine medical care and rehabilitation services for people with SCI [10]. Additionally, the economic impact of the pandemic has been severe, with many individuals losing their sources of income and facing increased financial insecurity [11]. In this challenging landscape, the Centre for the Rehabilitation of the Paralyzed (CRP) has played a crucial role in providing comprehensive care and rehabilitation services for individuals with spinal cord injuries in Bangladesh. Established in 1979 by Valerie Taylor, CRP has grown to become a leading institution in the country, offering a range of services including medical treatment, physical therapy, vocational training, and social integration programs [12]. The center is dedicated to enhancing the quality of life for people with disabilities and empowering them to achieve greater independence.

It's commonly known that the people with disabilities are the most vulnerable population in any pandemic situation, as they often may not be able to implement the required and nutrition, self-protection & hygiene [1]. In the current context, many people with disabilities have got an increased risk of contracting during COVID-19 and may have more difficulty in acting social distancing or self-isolation. After the COVID-19 has disrupted the daily structure and life routines of people all over the world including many people with SCI [13]. Social isolation for people with SCI is an issue that creates challenges for them, and in the many cases, caregivers must be socially isolated with the patients, resulting in extra costs needed in the family [14]. This study aims to explore the socio-economic impact of COVID-19 on people with spinal cord injury in Bangladesh. By conducting a telephonic survey, we seek to gather data on how the pandemic has affected their access to healthcare, employment, and overall well-being. This research will provide valuable insights into the specific needs of this vulnerable population and inform policy recommendations to improve their quality of life.

Objective of the study:

- To find out the socioeconomic status of person with SCI.
- To identify the response mechanism of the person with SCI.
- To find out the impact of Covid-19 the persons with SCI.

Materials and Methods

Researchers used a quantitative cross-sectional study design. The researcher used semi-structured questionnaires to determine the percentages of various variables connected to the person with SCI with large

sample sizes and collected data within a short period of time. The researcher used a comprehensive sampling method for collecting the data from the target population. The researcher conducted this study in urban, and rural areas of 08 divisions of Bangladesh. Participants list collected from the rehabilitation Wing department of CRP. The data was collected from the both male & female people with SCI who have discharged from CRP's inpatient facilities and resided at the communities during the Covid-19. Before conducting the study, ethical clearance (Ref No: 895) has been sought from the Institutional Review Board of the Bangladesh Health Professions Institute (BHPI). Permission was also obtained from the Rehabilitation Wing department of CRP and from the participants during the data collection period. Participants who had received rehabilitation service at CRP were contacted by phone. Persons with SCI were contacted over the phone because the participants were from different districts of Bangladesh. Trained interviewers conducted the phone calls with the persons with SCI who received rehabilitation service in the last 5 years, but the interviewers were able to collect data from 470 respondents because the rest of the participants did not respond and were not interested. During the data collection period, the interviewers clearly stated the purpose of the study and their participation rights in this study. Informed consent was obtained verbally from all participants before the telephonic survey. It also ensured that participants clearly understood the questions and provided accurate responses. Questionnaires consisted of demographic information and other questions related to finding the impacts on SCIs patients during Covid-19. Data entry and analysis were performed by using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), Inc. version 20.

Results

The study finds out the socio-economic impact of Covid-19 on people with SCI in Bangladesh through a telephonic survey of 470 participants. The results were presented in two main sections: demographic information and socio-economic impacts. Table 1 demonstrated the demographic breakdown of the participants. The age distribution of participants was as follows: 13% were 10-20 years, 26% were 21-30 years, 25% were 31-40 years, 21% were 41-50 years, and 15% were 51-60 years. Most participants were male (87%), with females representing 13% of the sample. About 30% of participants reported taking COVID-19 protection measures, while 65% had not taken any measures, and 5% were yet to consider taking any protection measures. On the other hand among those who received local Covid19 emergency aid, most of the participants (77%) didn't take the Covid-19 emergency

aid and only 18% received emergency aid and 5% indicated they did not need help from others. About 17% of respondents have participated in Covid-19 protection and prevention awareness events whereas only 15% of people with SCI have followed the principle of home quarantine. Most of the participants about 68% didn't take any protection measures.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Participants

Variable	N=470	Percentage (%)
Age range		
10-20 Years	61	13%
21-30 Years	122	26%
31-40 Years	118	25%
41-50 Years	99	21%
51-60 Years	70	15%
Gender		
Male	409	87%
Female	61	13%
Covid-19 protection measures		
Yes	141	30%
No	305	65%
Yet to think	24	05%
Types of protection measures taken		
Participated in Covid19 awareness	80	17%
No action taken	319	68%
Home Quarantine	71	15%
Home Sterilized	00	0%
Received local Covid-19 emergency aid		
Covid19 emergency aid	85	18%
None	362	77%
No need help	23	05%

Table 2 also demonstrated the socio-economic impacts experienced by the participants during the Covid-19 pandemic. The impact on livelihoods were varied, with 52% of participants reporting their business or economic activities were "bad," 12% said their business was "not good enough," 15% managed to maintain a "good" status, 10% experienced "less income," 1% had "no income," 1% stated their situation was the "same as previous," 4% described their situation as "very bad," and 5% did not respond the answer. A significant majority, 78%, indicated they required Covid-19 related support, 17% did not need any kind of support, and 5% did not respond. The above-mentioned reveals that 52% of interviewed people with SCI have sought any financial support to meet their due needs. Some of 17% respondents also seek fund to reinstate their shop well. As multiple responses 12% people with SCI have had different types need during these difficult times imposed by Covid-19. Supports for shop opens need 10%. The data indicate that the Covid-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted the livelihoods of people with

spinal cord injuries in Bangladesh, with a severe economic impacts and expressing the needs and supports to cope with the crisis.

Table 2: Socio-Economic Impacts on People with Spinal Cord Injury

Variable	N=470	Percentage (%)
Status of livelihood during Covid-19		
Business is not good enough	56	12%
Bad	244	52%
Good	71	15%
Less income	47	10%
No income	05	01%
Same as previous	05	01%
Very Bad	19	04%
No respond	23	05%
Covid-19 supports required		
Support required	367	78%
No Support required	80	17%
No respond	23	05%
Types of supports required		
Financial Supports	244	52%
Shop reinstate support	80	17%
Assistive device supports	14	03%
Vocational Training supports	09	02%
Treatment Support	05	01%
Cash & Relief	05	01%
Emergency Supports (any)	09	02%
Poultry & Animal Husb.	00	00%
Support for shop opens	47	10%
Multiple responses (for livelihood support)	57	12%

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the insightful socio-economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on persons with SCI in Bangladesh. The demographic profile shows that 87% of the participants were male, and 13% were female. This gender difference could reflect the broader societal trends in Bangladesh, where males are more likely to be the primary earners and thus more affected by economic disruptions [15]. A qualitative study found that persons with SCI have 70% low socio-economic status and the majority of them are unemployed 31.25% [16]. The age distribution of the participants, 26% were 21-30 years and 25% were 31-40 years. A prospective cross-sectional study found that 86.95% were male and 13.04% were female where 70.5% of participants age range between 19 to 40 years [17]. Another Socio-demographic and injury-related study found that 120 (83% men) participants with SCI; their median (interquartile range) age and injury duration were 34 (25-43) years and 5 (2-10) years, respectively [18].

A significant proportion of participants (65%) did not take any COVID-19 protection measures, which may be due to a lack of resources, awareness, or accessibility to necessary supplies of Personal protective equipment (PPE). Only 30% took protective measures, such as participating in Covid-19 awareness activities (17%) or home quarantine (15%). This low engagement in protective measures is concerning, given the heightened vulnerability of individuals with SCI to infections [19]. Another study found that during the Covid-19 period, the participants were quarantined [20]. Furthermore, only 18% received local Covid-19 emergency aid, and the majority of this population (77%) did not received any available support programs. This finding closely aligns with broader research that indicates that individuals with disabilities often face barriers to accessing emergency aid due to factors such as lack of information, physical inaccessibility, and social stigma [21, 22]. Urhan et al, (2021) also stated that in the pandemic situation working and economic life directly affect high-quality healthcare services and getting necessary medical supplies [23].

The socio-economic data indicates that 52% of participants reported their business or economic activities as "bad," and an additional 12% found their business "not good enough." Only 15% reported a "good" status, while 10% experienced reduced income and 4% described their situation as "very bad." A study in Nepal highlights the severe economic distress experienced by people with SCI during the pandemic, with a significant majority facing substantial financial challenges [24]. Another study found that Most of the participants were unemployed and fired from work due to disability [25]. Another study found that to spread the disease in lockdowns, enforced quarantines and other public health policy measures are sometimes required, and It affects the socioeconomic, educational, and career outcomes which may be socially disadvantaged [25, 26]. Gupta et al., (2011) states that PWD experienced financial difficulties associated with their disability, and returning to employment after suffering a SCI is complex [27]. A high percentage of participants (78%) shared that they required support during the pandemic, with many types of support requiring financial support (52%), support to reinstate shops (17%), and assistive device support (3%). A quality of life study in Japan found that this diverse range of needs reflects the multifaceted impact of the pandemic on the daily lives and livelihoods of individuals with SCI [28]. A Bangladesh study found that when trying to reintegrate into the Bangladeshi community, people with disabilities face different obstacles and challenges in transportation, accessibility, and physical and socioeconomic barriers in their surroundings [29]. Effective community

reintegration is considered an important demonstrator of a better quality of life [30].

The results of this study have several important implications, Firstly there is a need for targeted public health initiatives to increase awareness and accessibility of Covid-19 protection measures among people with SCI. Secondly, the significant demand for financial support and livelihood reinstatement emphasizes the necessity for supporting economic programs to address the unique needs of this vulnerable group. This includes not only direct financial aid but also support for vocational training and employment opportunities to help individuals regain their economic stability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound socio-economic impact on persons with SCI in Bangladesh. The findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to address the unique challenges faced by this vulnerable group. It also shows that persons with SCI not only face the fear and stress of Covid-19 but also face problems with economic and healthcare support. Most of them try to facilitate their income source but they are bound to loans and other issues. Policymakers and healthcare providers must prioritize inclusive and equitable responses to public health emergencies to ensure that no one is left behind.

Impact of this Research on the Future

The findings highlight the public health initiatives and economic support programs people with SCI. Policymakers can use this data to create inclusive policies that ensure these group of individuals receive adequate healthcare, financial aid, and support services during crises. The research shows the necessity for inclusive disaster management strategies that consider the needs of people with SCI. Future emergency preparedness plans can integrate specific measures to protect and support individuals with SCI and other disabilities.

Limitations

The study was conducted with a small number of persons with SCI. As a developing country, here resources were limited in this context. The researcher focused on SCIs who had completed the rehabilitation from CRP, making it challenging to represent all SCIs in Bangladesh.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interest.

Ethical Approval

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) of BHPI approved this study.

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